

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF THE SEEDS OF *LUFFA ACUTANGULA* ROXB.

A. K. BARUA, SACHINDRA K. CHAKRABORTI AND ASIT KUMAR RAY

A crystalline bitter principle, cucurbitacin B and an acid saponin, oleanolic acid, have been isolated and identified from the seeds of *Luffa acutangula* Roxb.

Luffa acutangula Roxb. (Family *Cucurbitaceae*, commonly known as *Jhinga* in Bengali) is cultivated as a vegetable throughout India. Martin de la Torre and Santos (*Rev. filipina med. farm.*, 1939, 30, 169; *Chem. Abst.*, 1939, 33, 5593) isolated a bitter substance, $C_{15}H_{24}O_4$, m.p. 182-84°, from *Luffa cylindrica* (Linn.) Roem. Rangaswami and Sambamurthy (*Indian J. Pharm.*, 1954, 16, 225) also reported the isolation of a bitter principle, m.p. 182-84°, from the seeds of *L. cylindrica* Roem., known in Bengal as *dhundul*. Choudhury, Sharma and Siddiqui (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1951, 10B, 26) obtained a bitter principle, designated as 'amarin', $C_{15}H_{24}O_5$, m.p. 182°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 88^\circ$ (ethanol), from the seeds of *L. acutangula* Roxb., var. *amara* Clarke. We have examined the seeds of *L. acutangula* Roxb. and the report of our preliminary investigation is mentioned herein.

From the ether extract of the defatted seeds was isolated in good yield (0.67%) a highly crystalline, colorless, bitter substance, which on chromatographic resolution on a column of cellulose powder, impregnated with formamide, gave a colorless crystalline compound, m.p. 175-82°, as the major product. A slightly higher melting fraction was also obtained during chromatography, but due to poor yield further work could not be carried out. The fraction (m.p. 175-82°) on repeated crystallisation from aqueous methanol and ethanol gave a constant melting compound, $C_{32}H_{48}O_8$, m.p. 182-85°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 87.4^\circ$ (96% ethanol).

From the alcoholic extract of the seeds a crude saponin in low yield was also isolated, which on hydrolysis gave an acid saponin, $C_{30}H_{48}O_8$, m.p. 304-308°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 78.3^\circ$ (chloroform). Barua and Bose (*Trans. Bose Res. Inst.*, 1956-57, 21, 19; * Barua, *Science & Culture*, 1957, 23, 154) also isolated the same acid from the seeds of *L. cylindrica*. The monomethyl ester of the acid, $C_{31}H_{50}O_8$, m.p. 198-200°, furnished a monoacetate, $C_{33}H_{52}O_4$, m.p. 222°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 70.4^\circ$ (chloroform). The acid saponin was identified as oleanolic acid by the determination of mixed m.p. of the methyl ester of the compound with an authentic sample of methyl oleanolate.

Recently Enslin *et al.* (*J. Sci. Fd. Agric.*, 1954, 9, 410; 1956, 7, 646 *et seq*) reported the isolation of a bitter principle, cucurbitacin B, $C_{28}H_{40-42}O_7$, m.p. 180-82°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 87.5^\circ$ (ethanol), from several plants of the *Cucurbitaceae* family and subsequently reported (*South African Ind. Chem.*, April, 1957) a higher melting point, 184-86° and $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 88^\circ$ (96% ethanol) for cucurbitacin B. Rivett and Herbstein

(*Chem. & Ind.*, 1957, 393) suggested the molecular formula of the above compound to be $C_{22}H_{42}O_8$ on the basis of molecular weight determination by the X-ray method. The physical and chemical properties of the compound, isolated by the present authors (m.p. 182-85°), agreed closely with those of cucurbitacin B and their identity was established by mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of cucurbitacin B and also by paper chromatography. It appears that cucurbitacin B is identical with 'amarin', reported by the Indian and Philippine workers (*loc. cit.*) from *Luffa* species. From a private communication from Dr. P. R. Enslin, we came to learn that a crude extract obtained by them from the seeds of *L. acutangula* gave a strong spot for cucurbitacin B on paper chromatogram.

*E X P E R I M E N T A L

Isolation of Cucurbitacin B.—Air-dried, powdered seeds (2 kg.) were defatted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and then extracted with ether in a Soxhlet apparatus for 30 hours. The ether extract was concentrated to a small volume (100 c.c.) and left overnight when a crystalline mass separated. On filtration and washing with a small quantity of ether, colorless crystals, m.p. 170-75°, were obtained. A second crop of crystals was obtained on further concentrating the mother-liquor and diluting with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), total yield 13.4 g.

The above material (1 g.) was dissolved in benzene (15 c.c.) and was adsorbed on a column (28 cm × 2 cm) of formamide-impregnated cellulose powder (25% formamide in ethanol). The column was eluted with 300 c.c. of petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) and the residue left on evaporation of the solvent melted at 175-82°. The column was then eluted with 250 c.c. of petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°)-benzene mixture (3:1), which gave a further amount of the above substance. On elution with the same solvent mixture (1:1, 300 c.c. and 1:3, 200 c.c.) a fraction, m.p. 190-200°, in very poor yield, was obtained. The residue from the petroleum ether fraction was repeatedly crystallised from aqueous ethanol and methanol to give a constant melting crystalline compound, m.p. 182-85°. This was found to be bitter and it responded to the Liebermann-Burchardt test. The m.p. of this compound was not depressed when admixed with an authentic sample of cucurbitacin B. (Found: C, 68.98; H, 8.73. Calc. for $C_{22}H_{42}O_8$: C, 68.54; H, 8.63%).

The crude bitter principle was also subjected to fractional crystallisations from aqueous ethanol when the fractions: (1) m.p. 180-85°, (2) m.p. 190-98° and (3) m.p. 207-22° were obtained. The last two fractions were obtained in extremely poor yield and therefore could not be further studied.

Paper Chromatography of the Bitter Principle.—The bitter principle was subjected to paper chromatography by following the technique of Enslin *et al.* (*J. South African Chem. Inst.*, 1954, 7, 131) to study the homogeneity and also for comparison with an authentic sample of cucurbitacin B. In our experiments, we used Whatman No. 1 filter paper, impregnated with 25% formamide in ethanol, and adopted the ascending method of development. The spots were conveniently located by their

* The m.p.'s are uncorrected. The microanalyses of the samples were carried out by Mrs. C. Dutta.

quenching in the ultraviolet light and also by spraying with 0.5% solution of $KMnO_4$ in saturated copper acetate. Our compound was co-chromatographed with the authentic sample of cucurbitacin B. The crude material also gave only one strong spot for cucurbitacin B. The R_f values of our compound in chloroform at 29° and in benzene at 28° are 0.91 and 0.63 respectively and those of the authentic sample of cucurbitacin B are 0.90 and 0.64 respectively.

Isolation of the Saponin.—The defatted material after extraction with ether was Soxhleted with alcohol (95%) for 40 hours. The dark brown syrupy mass obtained after removal of the solvent was repeatedly washed with ether (total 500 c.c.). The ether-insoluble gummy residue gave the tests for saponin.

Hydrolysis of the Saponin: Isolation of Oleanolic Acid.—The above residue was hydrolysed with 5% alcoholic hydrochloric acid for 4 hours. The hydrolysed product was taken up in ether after precipitation with water. The ether extract was washed with aqueous caustic soda (5%) and the sodio salt of the acid was acidified when the acid sapogenin was obtained as a white amorphous mass (yield 2.5 g.). This on repeated crystallisation from aqueous ethanol gave the pure compound, m.p. $304-308^\circ$. (Found: C, 78.90; H, 10.56. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{48}O_3$: C, 78.89; H, 10.59%).

Methyl Ester of the Acid.—The methyl ester of the above acid was prepared with diazomethane in the usual way and was purified by column chromatography on acid-washed alumina. The ester was then crystallised from acetone and finally from ethanol, m.p. $198-200^\circ$. (Found: C, 79.17; H, 10.58. Calc. for $C_{31}H_{50}O_3$: C, 79.10; H, 10.71%). It did not depress the m.p. of an authentic sample of methyl oleanolate. The above methyl ester gave an acetate, m.p. 222° . The melting point was not depressed when admixed with an authentic sample of acetylmethyl oleanolate. (Found: C, 77.39; H, 10.31. Calc. for $C_{33}H_{52}O_4$: C, 77.30; H, 10.22%).

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